

Exploring Intersections: Fifth International Multimedia Event on Architecture

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Abstract

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Referring to Klaus Mainzer's theory and interpretation of move from symmetry toward complexity (Mainzer, 2005) considering his explanation of complexity theory through various scientific frameworks – mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology, economics and social sciences, computer science, philosophy, and arts - additionally extending its influences on many matters covered by research in principles of nonlinearity, a distinctive view on its application in architecture has been revealed and problematized as a specific subject of scientific interest. The architectural design aimed at engaging time and change, transformation, shifting scales, mobility, multiplicity of views, programs/scenarios, and forms, interactivity and inner reconfiguration and self-constructing capacities of architectural systems, renders a specific mapping of complexity offering new measures and strategies of its dynamic control and skillful articulation.

Complexity theory, the study of nonlinear dynamic systems, has been used as a conceptual framework that “reconciles the essential unpredictability with the emergence of distinctive patterns” (Cartwright, 1991) – “It suggests that simple deterministic functions can give rise to highly complex and often unpredictable behavior, and yet this complexity can still exhibit surprising order and patterns” (Levy, 2000:68). Without simple cause and effect relationships, or a single and easily discernible rule of progression and development, the systems analyzed are based on more complex algorithms and relational laws between the elements that constitute them. Their dynamic properties are essential for being characterized by “nonlinear relationships and complex interactions that evolve dynamically over time”

(Levy, 2000:68; Tran, in Erçetin and Bağcı, 2016:169).

Following system theory, theory of complexity and chaos, dynamic systems theory, and design intelligence strategies (D. Ciric) as ways of articulating multiple data diagrammatically in architecture and its extended meta-disciplinary field, the paper deals with their problems and architectural interpretation through different studies and research projects. Diagrammatization of dynamic processes here refers to scientific refinement and definition of their properties as basic motives and principles of architectural research (work with data and organizing structures, or intensive properties with specific spatial effects) and architectural design (e.g. investigation through iterative processes and versioning).

intelligence

The aim of this paper is to investigate the possibilities of contemporary application of complexity theory and its branches developed under different scientific frameworks, within the field of architecture. Besides application of complexity logic in design issues, the very architecture of complexity may be analyzed as a concept and concrete structural response to intricate spatial conditions and main building/design thinking properties and parameters (formal, programmatic, logical, social, aesthetic, or all of them at the same time). It leads toward conclusion with structures of non-linear development and instability – a design of an interactive, dynamic quantum-operative digital field in support of the proposed cognitive strategy (design intelligence strategy, Ciric, 2017), merging its diagrammatic and dynamic properties towards its quantum computing and modeling. This quantum-like dynamics application to cognition (Broekaert, Basieva, Blasiak, Pawel, and Pothos, 2017) and its resulting architecture (the structure of its spatial distribution) represent the ultimate mode of architectural interpretation of “complex dynamic adaptable systems and networking” as a register of higher metacognitive design operations and performances articulating highly complex memory archives and data-scapes in an open system quantum model.

Microlines of Complexity:

The Brief View on Historical Origins and the Recent History of Complexity

The recent history records several important moments in development of studies in complexity. This implies structured research framework and application as a distinctive scientific system which distinguishes it from the previously integrated cross-disciplinarity of the natural philosophy and science. Introduction of such complexity can be traced in several scientific revolutions (Morin, 2006:17). The first one emerged in a marginal fashion in mathematics and engineering of the 19th century, and it was connected to discoveries within the field of thermodynamics. This happened “when complexity overruled simple mechanisms” following the moment of failure of the Newtonian Paradigm through new scientific explanation of the world we live in (Mikulesky in Jonas, 2007): Newton’s gravitation theory had to be replaced by Einstein’s general relativity theory, Maxwell’s electrodynamics enlarged by special relativity theory, and quantum mechanics by quantum field theories, especially quantum electrodynamics (Meinzer, 2005:9-10). With these changes, 20th century encountered two scientific movements. The first one was “that of the microphysics and cosmophysics that introduced indeterminism and risk where determinism reigned” elaborating suitable methods to deal with uncertainties (Morin, 2006:17-18). This movement achieved its peak in the second half of the 20th century, developing the new scientific field, subject matter, methodologies and theoretical framework from integrative knowledge and network of collaborative sciences. The Earth sciences (which designed Earth as a complex physical system, making possible today to articulate geology, seismology, volcanology, meteorology, ecology, etc.), as well as space sciences, converged number of disciplinary knowledges in order to explain the complex nature of interdependency and intricacy of all the elements of the “real” physical world in the light of new complexity theory. Namely, “ecology, cosmology, and Earth sciences have become poly-disciplinary sciences, even transdisciplinary” (Morin, 2006:18), while later the same concept will be applied in biology and social sciences. The idea of self-organization and nonlinear behaviour brought finally unpredictability and nonpredictive causality effects to that level of quantum probability that it had to be stated as completely incomprehensible or “wicked” (such as the “effect of the observer”, quantum superposition, or multiverse). The third complexity revolution may be identified in some recent attempts of complexity theory revision and advancement through contemporary information, natural and social sciences, and digital articulation of almost every field of research. This last actually represents the moment of technological evidence and realization of all the previous concepts while innovation is articulated through various disciplinary transfers and integration in production and design of the new creative complexity models.

Complex reasoning, representation, and problematization could be found all along historical lines of various artistic and scientific practices. Here, they take the form of knowledge as practiced before the formal institutional disciplinary systematization. The cosmopoietic constructs (including structure, spatiality, natural and artificial environment, complete knowledge, laws and policies, beliefs, social

relations, cultural values, etc. of societies) dealt with complexity within the attempt to define the world and the universe as completely synchronized entity. They were ruled by superior natural-social principles which defined the ways of their reasoning and representation (mythological/religious, metaphysical/philosophical, or physical/scientific). Traces of this worldly complexity and the attempts to integrate multiplicity of heterogenic autonomies having their own existence on different parallel timelines

(Delanda, 1998, 2000) into the one comprehensive entity, are documented in numerous examples of intricate organizing and operative principles. They may refer to practices of mapping and cartographic world representations, philosophical and metaphysical explanations of their dynamics, or organization of society and social structures, diagrammatically spatially represented as reflection of the geo- and astrometrics. These complex maps may be the highest systemic forms merging all the relevant subsystems into the one superior whole. As reflections of the common social, state, spatial/territorial (terrestrial and celestial), and economic orders/harmonics/regulations, or the main logic behind the ruling cultural values and realities, these complex patterns in historical examples might be placed on the foundational platform of some contemporary examples of complex thinking. Specifically, at architectural or urban scales, they might be interpreted in spatial design of the living environment that converges space-time-society-culture as a synthetic entity - society as a form of complex dynamic spatiality (referring to social-spatial specificity, Soja, 2000).

Figure 1: Cosmopoietic mapping- world representation and reasoning
a. 1718 Circular historical diagram of the Roman empire, Italy, and neighboring countries to 1700
b. 1820, Boselli, Giovanni, Francesco Milano. Pianta topografica
c. 1734 Gerard van Keulen, De Nieuwe Groot Lichtende Zee Fakkell., Image courtesy of the Harvard Map Collection.
d. Ebstorf Mappamundi, 113, Christian World <http://www.landschaftsmuseum.de/Seiten/Museen/Ebstorf1.htm>
GPischke "History of Geo- and Space Sciences", 2014, Vol. 5, No. 2, pp. 149 –
e. Geometric construction from Claudius Ptolemy's Almagest—originally published in 2nd century CE
(translation by Gerard of Cremona, 15th century).
f. Hereford Mappa Mundi 1300, Richard of Haldingham, Hereford Cathedral, Hereford, UK (in *Jersey Maps: The World's Masterpieces Explored and Explained*)
g. Table III. The Dimensions of the Orbits of the Planets, and their Distances, Exhibited by means of the Five Regular Geometric Bodies Dedicated to the most Illustrious Prince...Frederick, Duke of Wirtemberg." [Johannes Kepler, *Cosmographicum, frontispiece, 1594.*] (Comp. fol. 214), Joannis Kepleri: Opera Omnia Volumen I, (Ed. Christoph)

Even though these complex or complicated representations might testify to the possible existence of the scientific concepts of complexity a lot earlier than it has been suggested (Morin, 2006), the key criterion distinguishing contemporary from the historical complexity includes scientific construction and explanation of complex systems, establishment of their principles, logic, and structure, and the extension toward the questions of their generative and evolutive character, dynamic and unpredictable behaviour. Existing intellectual and theoretical bases and conventions stand for this kind of definition of the scientific complexity as opposed to historical one developed earlier. Still, historical examples directly related to some of the most advanced contemporary concepts may be those of digital and diagrammatic information processing (Ciric, 2017). They are proposed here as referential historical scripts of complexity (representations of applied scientific studies including mathematics, geometry,

logic, and semantics, scientific classification and organization of different systems of knowledge) which, if compared to contemporary complexities, would fit within the classes of information complexities - combinatorial, organizational complexity of the digital era and codified systematization. Dynamic complexities, conversely, may be found in rare cases (as dynamic notations) and still not properly scientifically explained as those in 19th and 20th century. Dynamic property marked as evolutive, genetic, generic, adaptable, or nonlinear, is precisely the one making difference between the historical and contemporary concepts of complexity.

Figure 2 a. Diagrams of Lull's intriguing combinatorial-logic concepts, from Lull, *Ars Brevis V.M.B. Raymundi Lullij Tertij Ord. S. Francisci, Doc. Illu.: mendis castigata, Capitibus Divisa, atque schollis locupletata*, 1669, in Lima, Manuel. Visual Complexity, fig.13, p.32
 b. *Arbor scientiae* (Tree of science), from Ramon Lull, *Arbor scientiae venerabilis et caelitus illuminati Patris Raymundi Lullii maioricensis Liber ad omnes scientias utilissimus*, 1515, in Lima, Manuel. Visual Complexity, fig.11, p.32
 c. *Geometry*, from Christophe de Savigny, *Tableaux accomplis*, 1587. in Lima, Manuel. Visual Complexity, fig.14, p.35

Figure 3 a. Burak Arikan, *Growth of a Twitter Graph, 2008* (A map of connections within a user's Twitter network, grouped by topics of interest), in Lima, Manuel. Visual Complexity, fig., p.152
 b. Jacob Ratkiewicz et al. *Truthy, 2010* (A diffusion network of the Twitter #GOP hashtag using Truthy, a system to analyze and visualize the diffusion of information on Twitter. Truthy evaluates thousands of tweets an hour to identify new and emerging bursts of activity around different memes), in Lima, Manuel. Visual Complexity, fig. p.152

COMPLEXITY THEORY AND LOGIC OF COMPLEX FORMATIONS

Complexity theory is the study of complex, nonlinear, dynamic systems with feedback effects. For the sake of clarity, chaos theory is here distinguished from network theory, and the term "complexity" is used as an umbrella concept that includes both chaos and networks. Chaos theory is concerned with systems in which the recursive application of nonlinear deterministic functions can give rise to apparent random behavior and subtle patterns. (Levy, L. David)

Starting with the initiative of development of "general systems theory" in the 1950s and 1960s, scientists were trying to come up with the universal principles which would be applicable to diverse forms of (complex) systemic entities (Herbert, 1962:467). Implying a kind of meta-logic as a set of common properties and criteria by which diverse systems could be defined, systems theory represented

a promising point of view. However, it was obvious that such diversity cannot be completely covered by a single formula if the aim was to maintain particularities of the subject matter (physical, biological, social systems, etc.), but as a concept which aimed at their scientific formalization and system of explanation, the initial idea of complexity theory stood for an important issue in every scientific field. The concept originated from definition of natural and social formations and their behaviour containing properties of change, transformation, evolution, or any kind of generic development, expressing additionally properties of instability, inconsistency, relativity, or uncertainty – a “wicked unpredictability”. They are considered to be very complicated in their procedural patterns, and as such are signified with the term of complex

systems. It is said that “A system is complex when it is composed of many parts that interconnect in intricate ways.” (Joel Moses, “Complexity and Flexibility”). A definition has to do with the number and nature of interconnections, but the measure of intricateness represents the priority criteria of complexity whose “... degree and nature of the relationships are imperfectly known” and as a consequence of their intricacy the overall emergent behavior is difficult to predict, even when subsystem’s behavior is readily predictable (Joseph Sussman, 1999); their measurement is noisy or unachievable (Robert L. Flood and Ewart R. Carson). The relations are dynamic, possibly irregular, and variously dependent so that small changes in input parameters may produce large changes in behaviour (e.g. butterfly effect). In these terms, “the system presents dynamic complexity when cause and effect are subtle, over time.” (Peter Senge, “The Fifth Discipline”) – it expresses dramatically different effects in the short-run and the long-run, and dramatically different effects locally and in other parts of the system; obvious interventions produce nonobvious consequences (Senge). In complex systems, the character of the elements and their interrelations are highly variable (elusive), left open, thus susceptible to functioning in an intricate way, producing complicated relations.

Simplicity-Complexity

The shift from simplicity to complexity in historical terms is usually related to the period between the 17th and 19th century when “physical science learned variables” and developed further from problems of simplicity (Weaver, 1948:1). The actual turn from simple regular systemic explanation came with scientific advancement in comprehension of living things and different natural and social phenomena as situations in which “numerous quantities are all varying simultaneously and in subtly interconnected ways” (Weaver, 1948:2). Analytical model dealing with billions of variables developed techniques of probability theory and statistical mechanics for the problem of disorganized complexity (completely unpredictable, hence uncontrollable type of complexity containing large number of variables whose behaviour is individually erratic or totally unknown, and their effects/(chain of) events “shrouded in mystery” (Weaver, 1948:3)) and organized complexity not differing largely in number of variables, but in specific property of organization.

In 1948, Weaver defined major types of systemic principles – simplicity on the one hand, and organized and disorganized complexity on the other. Simon adopted his definitions and, in 1962 explained development of complexity theory through his own theory of hierarchy (Simon, 1962:468). His definition argued for unpredictable and nonregular relations and non-simple interactions among the elements as major complexity criteria, but he spanned the problem of complex systems forming their basic understanding on near-decomposability (decomposable nature of complex systems) and the fact that different types of complexities emerged or evolved from simplicity (Simon, 1962). Later on, the concept of continuity and connectome-properties replaced, in some cases, discrete systems and decomposable understanding of complex formations and activities through scientific recoding (Simon, 1962:478) (In architectural design, consequent application of differential geometry and topology, or continuous movement calculus express this turn and can be traced through theories of dynamism at the beginning of the 20th century, their discrete application until 1970s, theories of constant flux in 1990s, behaviour of the natural dynamic CAS and morphogenesis in 2000s and 2010s, etc.)

In search for a general method, or an algorithm that could explain the behavior of complex systems (the law and the rule by which they are generated and consequently act), Wolfram used dynamic systems theory and theory of computation. By building different models of complex systems, he showed that

principle of simplicity in their construction (used either in definition of elements or the evolving rule) could produce very complex results and effect, determining system's behavior as extremely complicated and therefore difficult to predict (Wolfram, 1985). The rule of development (and the pattern of growth as its recognizable inner mechanism) was what defined a degree of simplicity/complexity – “improbability of very complicated arrangements (reached by some kind of evolutive or another process) is what made a criterion of simplicity relevant at all” (Wolfram, 1985). Wolfram participated in complex systems theory's development initiating foundation of the first institute devoted to the subject (CCRS), starting additionally the journal *Complex Systems* in 1987. At this point, the main reason for complex system theory popularity was related to the prevalence of cybernetics and domination of research in control theory (Wolfram, 1985:6).

In some recent revisions on complexity theory, we may mark its representation as the new meta-tool for dealing with different complexities (Jonas, 2007), referring to suggestions by Bar-Yam (“complex = consisting of interconnected or interwoven parts / not easy to understand or analyze, and - complexity = the amount of information needed to describe it” (Bar-Yam, 1997, in Jonas, 2007), Horgan's 31 definitions, and Mikulesky's claims among which his notions of complexity as being more about the function of

systems quality than size (Von Neuman previously thought that a critical level of system size would trigger the onset of complexity). Mikulecky equals complexity with the real world (reality), while simple mechanisms as defined by traditional scientific models embody formal systems which usually fail to explain precisely the phenomenon observed (Mikulecky, 2003). He also points out to their nonfragmentable nature, important in describing continuity and non-particularity of the subject matter which gets us closer to continuous change in dynamic systems and formal explanation related to non-Euclidean models as explained in mathematics and physics of spaces. Being “more than the sum of its parts” systems are defined by their relational nature, interactions and smooth change of behavior.

Symmetry-Complexity

The symmetry-complexity relation in Meinzer's work represents rather universal principles defined above all as mathematical and physical concepts, as well as applied in disciplines such as biology, chemistry, political and social sciences, information sciences, architecture and arts, education systems and neuroprocessing. Nuances in their concepts appear as a consequence of the knowledge of the epoch and the degree of social-cultural and scientific development. “Mathematically, symmetry is characterized by a group of transformations that leave certain features of a system unchanged” (Meinzer, 2005:8) and this is usually a property of regularity. A system characterized by a larger group of transformations has higher symmetry. “The symmetry of a system is broken when new features emerge that are not invariant under at least some of its transformations”; if dynamical systems become unstable in this way, they can jump from one state to another with a completely different pattern of behaviour (nonlinearity). These instabilities – cascades of bifurcations - can lead from order to chaos. Compared to concept of organized and disorganized complexity, Poincare's deterministic chaos may refer to this kind of an internal regular complexity containing determinable logic of the dynamic mechanism of system's behaviour and progression, while disorganized complexity entails complete unpredictability and variety in behaviour pattern – constant transition phase and fluctuation. Thus self-similarity and the fractal geometry reveal the mathematical beauty of symmetries even behind the nonlinear world of change and chaos – a dynamical symmetry (Mainzer, 2005:21) or regular dynamic complexity – while irregular/random dynamic complexity (unpredictable complexity) expresses bifurcation trees of nonlinear dynamics with larger number of chaos attractors (derived from Meinzer, 2005:99). In this respect, we recognize the whole realm of entities of the transition from highest symmetry (e.g. crystal) to perfect chaos and randomness (e.g. gases)” (Meinzer, 2005:14-15).

THE SCIENCE OF NETWORKS – LOGICS OF CONNECTIVITY

Figure 4 a. Chris Harrison, WikiViz, 2006 (intricate linking structure of Wikipedia), in Lima, Peru, Visual Complexity, p.156
b. Heath Bunting, Map of Terror, 2008. In Lima, Peru, Visual Complexity, p.141

Figure 5 a, b: "A Network Diagram for a Propositional Calculus" Martin Gardner, Logic Machines and Diagrams, New York, Toronto, London: McGraw-Hill Book Company, 1958, p. 67
c, d, e: Lull's combinatorial method. In every branch of knowledge, there is a small number of simple basic principles or categories that must be assumed without question. By exhausting all possible combinations of these categories we are able to explore all the knowledge that can be understood by our finite minds. To construct tables of possible combinations we call upon the aid of both diagrams and rotating circles. For example, we can list two sets of categories in two vertical columns (Fig 1) then exhaust all combinations simply by drawing connecting lines as shown. Or we can arrange a set of terms in a circle (Fig 2) draw connecting lines as indicated, then by reading around the circle we quickly obtain a table of permutations. A third method, and the one in which Lull took the greatest pride, is to place two or more set of terms on concentric circles (Fig 3). Martin Gardner, Logic Machines and Diagrams, New York, Toronto, London: McGraw-Hill Book Company, 1958, pp. 9-10
f: Ramon Lull, First Figure / First Enneagram (Enneagram of Personality), Ramon Llull, 1307
Palma de Mallorca BP MS998. Digital version Biblioteca Virtual del Patrimonio Bibliográfico. Spain. Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y Deporte. Iniani, Ernesto, "Ramon Llull", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Spring 2017 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2017/entries/llull/>

When speaking about the interactions among the constituents of complex systems and the nature of their connectivity, one undoubtedly refers to network theory. Time-related variation and diversity in connectivity within a given system - the generic rules of the trajectories of attraction - represent the central question of science of networks. Lines of connectivity, their intricacy, and change as the major indicator of complexity developed relational theory and relational approach to complex dynamic structures. Thus we speak about relational dynamics and consequent techniques of their mapping rendering patterns of relational change.

Even though science of networks existed much earlier throughout history, Watts' and Strogatz's paper in 1998 marks the moment of its contemporary advancement. At this point, its scientific framework has been reinforced by fully developed graph theory. It defined mathematical basis and new modelling tools for the investigation and visual representation of relatively tractable large-scale complex systems, quantifiable metrics for prediction of their complex interactions and behaviors, metrics and algorithms for extracting information from them in order to improve their "observability" (Magee, 2006:13). In comparison to historical examples (fig. 1), these networking models were dynamic, directly measuring and recording changes through time, but also recording particular moments as fixed distributions of their discretely defined variability. As such, they mapped regular patterns and symmetries created by simple or determinable rules of development, as well as intricate replication introducing difference and unpredictability of the final outcome.

According to the relational and organizing principles and rules of dynamic reconfiguration, we may distinguish several types of networking. The random network paradigm, (Erdős and Rényi, 1959)

assumed and modelled complex networks as random graphs. This led to the emergence of random networks as a new mathematical field of study, proposing network solutions such as WWW and the internet, economic currents, etc. Evolving networks represent characteristic type of constant change which, differing from the (traditional) problem-solving, have no final solution (evolution is a process of phase transitions with symmetry breaking and the emergence of new molecular structures, organisms, species, and populations. (Meinzer, 2005:18)). Evolving networks inscribe the pattern of the system which is never optimally adapted to the environment since the process of system's evolution changes the environment itself producing feedback loop for new adaptation. This process contains constant fluctuations of the interdependent entities. Systems correspond to what we call stable assemblies or emerging systems in the way that their identities appear as temporary in response to total conditions (internal and external interactions) including large number of systemic formations involved in dynamic coexistence. The complex evolution (parallel or distributed) implies multitude of systems evolving simultaneously, partially autonomously, partially in interaction (Heyligen, 2000). The "network" structure evolves in a way that no absolute distinction can be made between internal and external, between system and environment. When thinking of such absolutely global system (universe) where each system will have both an aspect of internal selection (intrinsic stability) and of external selection (adaptation), the model of multidimensional field variation around strange attractors comes to the forefront as their possible outmost spatial distribution. The ultimate network state of the dynamic relational category, considering each system as a dynamic field of some kind of physical unboundedness, could be named a field or swarm networking. The nature – structure and dynamics - of these networks is multiplex and time-varying.

Figure 6. a, b, c. Lorenz attractor
d. Jessica Buie, Calabi Yau Space Manifold, ink drawing

Reductionism and Emergence: Extensive and Intensive Properties

Besides the support of dynamic quality, complexity theory's quantifiable devices and methods frequently guided research towards reductionism. The main problem traditionally appeared on the border between mathematics as means of quantification and simplification, and other sciences dealing more directly with natural phenomena's uncontrolled, nonperfect/non-ideal dynamic behavior. With the change of the scientific system which will be explanatory for emergent processes, the notion of space had to be reevaluated - the theories of relativity, topology, dynamic systems, theory of the catastrophe, complex analysis, and even multiverse and string theory, entered the field of architecture, redefining its formative devices. Autopoietic systems were viewed through integrative, holistic concepts implying their real nature as always escaping stable spatial determination and closed formalisms, and the question of architectural design principles following these facts had to be raised. The boundaries of these systems, held by claim of their internal cohesion and coherence, are spatially made unstable by external-internal interactions and here the problem for architecture as a means of bordering, spatially articulating complexities, had to include dynamic properties in its design discourses.

Within the reductionism-emergence division as two main overarching organizing principles, reductionism would have been argued by traditional particle physicist (from the viewpoint of systemic subdivision and theory of elementary structure of all systems) while the condensed-matter physicist studying complex material/matter(s) would stand for the emergence (Dijkgraaf, 2017). However, convergence of these two laws, (proposed by quantum science, e.g. quantum gravity (Dijkgraaf: 2017)), is what is more likely to represent final scientific standpoint in contemporary moment. Functioning through multi-systemic intricacy, an elegant solution of the perception of the whole maintained overall dynamics of its meta-scape within which individual systems emerge as recognizable autonomous entities but not completely independent of the whole's dynamics influencing constant reconfiguration

processes. Elementary particularism becomes unattainable when number of particles (approaching infinity) and intricacy of their relations become incomprehensible and too complex to be analysed, calculated and represented traditionally. Emergent laws of dynamic systems view this problem differently, defining the law of transformation, not the elements performing it; “their approximate nature allows for a certain flexibility that can accommodate future evolution“ (Wheeler, in Dijkgraaf, 2017). Patterns emerge from the dynamic systems’ complex behaviour involving different kinds of its building units and blocks - “biochemical reactions give rise to sentient beings ... individual organisms gather into ecosystems ... all the celestial bodies make swirls of galaxies“ (Dijkgraaf, 2017). For architecture as spatial discipline, the question of interest made from these observations refers to their possible effect on the notions of architectural space-time, or architecture-organism-environment “formulas“.

Figure 7: D. Ciric, Metahistorical multiplicity of timelines and microhistorical connectivities – fragments investigation in *microhistorical paths within the metahistorical field of information* (D. Ciric, 2017) provided the tools for analysis by diagramming between scattered particles of new fields of knowledge; within its structure and ordering the issues of systems dynamics, and ideas of dynamism, variation, and complexity could be traced and recorded as scientific inferences. Elementarism and dynamism set their modern theoretical foundations in 1920s (questions of movement and continuity in futurism and representations of their structured, particle-based dynamic fields, or elementarism of the modern movement's structural studies); metabolism and structuralism of 1960s and 1970s, spanning scales from micro to macro levels, included systemic dynamic complexities into their inventions in construction and urban systems (Richard Buckminster Fuller's *Synergetics*, metabolists and their systemic view on cities and architecture, or architectural structuralism). Additional chaos theory and theory of the catastrophe, led architectural investigations towards deconstructivist ideas of structural breakage and tectonic approaches to questions of contextuality, dynamics and virtual theory (animated and fluid spaces) simultaneously supported by current scientific and philosophical paradigms. Contemporary continuity of these architectural research lines documents high influence of technology in dynamic and structural matter/field of architectural theory and practice, with the elevated reliability and precision of scientific data employed in spatial concepts and methodologies (e.g. strategies of form-finding (Fuller, 1960s; Ghery, 1980s, 1990s; Lynn, 1990-2000; 2010s), "form following climate" (Rahm, 2010s), programmatic dynamics based on analysis of mobility and behaviour of masses (UN studio) etc.). It may be additionally pointed out to publications such as *Emergence: Morphogenetic Design Strategies* (Hensel, Menges, Weinstock, 2004) and *The Architecture of Emergence* (Weinstock, 2010), directly dealing with self-organizing principles of complexity.

**DYNAMIC DESIGN INTELLIGENCE STRATEGY:
COMPLEX THINKING SYSTEMS, OPERATIVE STRUCTURES, AND LOGICS OF CONNECTIVITY**

Within the attempt to construct a model of design thinking – a design intelligence strategy (Ciric, 2017:525-527) – defined as complex dynamic structure of multiple data expressing property of

superposition, several criteria derived from complexity and networking theory are presented as formative for this kind of neural field. Design intelligence structural logic is defined by parameters such as diagrammatic thinking (relational skills of connectivity within the open fluid interactive systems), topological thinking (constructing topological space signifying the “space of probability”), and creative thinking (including chaos patterns and unpredictability in creating innovation through variation and versioning), but also multidimensional structuring, memory archiving, extensions and elasticity, and integral information processing. Additional properties of complex dynamics are introduced in order to explain their nature and functioning more precisely: design intelligence system is understood as complex adaptable dynamic system based on variation-selection, quantum-logic, properties of hybridization and emergence; it works as an advanced thinking structure in architectural decision making and design.

Dynamic systems behaviour

Dynamic system theory was developed to describe the global properties of solutions to differential equations. As these kinds of systems evade stable conditions being in constant movement, transformation, evolution or development, and could change their pattern of behaviour with the smallest deviation of what seemed to be its registered logic or an algorithm, their prediction becomes impossible. The only way to predict the system’s behaviour would be to simulate it if computationally reducible (Wolfram, 1985:5). But if the systems are irreducible, or no appropriate formula for its mathematical, computational, or physical explanation is defined, conventional theoretical methods cannot be applied. As irreducibility to computer parameters in order to perform simulations could represent a significant obstacle, one of the main tasks for computing thinking processes is this operationalization of dynamism (quantum computing).

Complex Systems Adaptability

Knowledge domain construction of the Complex Adaptive Systems (CAS) and Complexity Theory is related to the activity of the Santa Fe school of thought back in the mid-1980s (Dodder and Dare, 2000). Originating from different disciplines, their founders aimed towards development of subject of complexity and its terminology through this formal cross-disciplinarity (Holland (1993): Holland, 1995, in Jonas, 2007). From here, CAS-thinking in physics, biology, economics, archaeology, and political science established foundations for other disciplines, providing also some scientific direction for architectural research, shaping distinctive lines of thought in architectural theory and practice.

Opposing ideal complexity (based on a complex progression of the simple unit, or producing complex patterns by simple iterative algorithm), usually understood as developing symmetries by bifurcations of their own irrespective of the environment, inter-systemic or multiple interactions adaptability includes constant synchronization with other objects-systems or all-pervading one. A system undergoes variation while environment exerting a “selective pressure” on the system (Heylighen, 2000:2). The evolving system resolves the system-environment (or additionally system-system and environment-environment) problem generating possible solutions by trial (variation) including optimization, which will be confirmed by its possible or apparent stability. If the adaptation response is not optimal, i.e. the system is not perfectly stable with respect to the environment, the variation continues: “The larger the instability, the more serious the problem, and the more variation the system must undergo before it reaches a new equilibrium.” (Heylighen, 2000:2). But, considering the property of constant adaptation (fluctuations based on infinite interactions) system performs continuous transformations around possible stabilities (strange attractors) never to achieve its equilibrium. The CAS is therefore defined by processes it performs in relation to this stable condition and other systems.

Developed between the internal and external processes (even though in emergent forms this border is completely erased within the integrative metascape), adaptability still implies division on multiple systemic entities, based on mutual interchangeable influences. It retains the duality between internal and external selection, further applied to variation. Internal variation (selforganizing activity), a process in which an inner part of a system is changed, may be triggered by external influences, and external variation means that the relation between the system and its environment is changed - that the system is coupled to different external systems, or that a property from the environment might be changed as a consequence of some kind of internal influence (Heylighen, 2000:3).

Figure 8: a. Wind @ 500hPa + Total Cloud Water - 2017-0324 22:00 Local UT, 28.38° S, 151.86° E 185° @ 46 km/h, 0.016 kg/m2
Stereographic Projection, GFS / NCEP / US National Weather Service
https://earth.nullschool.net/#2017/03/24/2100Z/wind/isobaric/500hPa/overlay=total_cloud_water/stereographic=144.37-13.78,2546/loc=151.860,-28.379
b. c. Phillippe Rahim-Domestic astronomy Louisiana Museum of Modern Art, 2009,

Variation-selection dynamics

The problem of definition of dynamic system which assumes constant change and fluctuations includes the necessity of determining what is or should be stable or invariant – an identity indicator. That internal criterion is called the strange attractor – a stable condition which draws near the system but which is never achieved as in reality this model itself also changes according to systemic interactions. The identity of a system is a property which distinguishes it from the background/environment or other entities. The system emerges, its state may change, but the invariant properties provide closures which constitute system's identity (e.g. if system has a variable structure it may maintain organizational principle (“organizational closure”), or an operative algorithm). Heylighen introduces “relational closure” as a concept that could explain invariant parameters either mathematically or conceptually (Heylighen 1989, 2000). He also defines four basic closures within the generic concept of transformation – transitive or recursive, cyclical, surjective, and inverse surjective (Heylighen, 1989, 2000). Their combinations, further, form the base for orthocomplemented lattices, and hence for Boolean algebras.

The same element or subsystem may be part of different “closures” or higher order systems – the element interacts on different levels and may form permanent, temporary, or transitory functional structures and configurations - which is why these different organizations or architectures cannot be neatly separated. The overall architecture of interactions between the elements is “a superposition of all partial organizations” (Heylighen, 2000:5), dynamic configurations established while fluctuating around possible stabilities. Heylighen's implication to an overall merged system, or Simon's non-hierarchical system and non-linear self-organizing model, resemble here proposed metacognitive scape and open structure which allows dynamic non-fixed interactions and constant change of connectivities among the elements without the need of any permanent stability. These rules include open networking decision for structural entities – quantum-like dynamics and multiple possible interactions.

The quantum logic/parameter

Recently, the concept of the second quantum revolution was introduced (Jaeger, Khrennikov, and Perinotti, 2017) to mark current development in quantum experimentation and technology, and new kinds and fields of their application. Implying to the problems such as “the role of contextuality in quantum theory, the derivation of this formalism from natural operational and probabilistic principles, and the applicability of the mathematical formalism of quantum theory (especially quantum probability and quantum information) outside of quantum physics, e.g. in decision theory“, the possibilities of concept's exit from the initial scientific field of physical sciences or foundational mathematics initiated thinking about its design application. The use of the mathematical formalism of quantum theory in modelling of the (design) decision-making process (with the aid of theory of open quantum systems) could be specifically applied in construction of cognitive neural networks of quantum-like nature. Highly corresponding to current techniques and explanations in neurosciences and information sciences, representing adaptability principles of decision making by information environment of quantum fields, this approach becomes of the enormous value for research of architecture/structure of cognition, as well as possible architectural figures generated through these properties. Recent investigations in

neurocognition in building of memory archives and data-scapes, coincide with quantum model in various descriptions of its intelligence strategy (Ciric, 2017). Previous models (Bagarello, Haven, Khrenikov, and Perinotti) and above mentioned one of quantum-like dynamics application to cognition (Broekaert,

Basieva, Blasiak, Pawel, and Pothos, 2017) could help in designing interactive quantum operative digital field of proposed cognitive strategy (design intelligence) - its quantum computing.

Figure 9: D. CiriDatascape—non-hierarchical open structure field of data with quantum logic of interaction and relational connectivity among the elements information chatter: Metahistorical multiplicity of timelines/systems translated in metacognitive scape

The mathematical model of decision-making (DM) of agents acting in a complex and uncertain environment (combining huge variety of economic, financial, behavioural and geopolitical factors), represents interaction of agents constructed as formalism of quantum field theory (QFT) (Bagarello, Haven, Khrennikov, 2017). This model applies quantum logic and field distribution within the information research and artificial digital cognitive networking operations. Defining mathematically quantum and adaptable relations in QFT model (using operator representation in Hilbert space and describing adaptability as quantum dynamics), the solution, which in these kinds of systems are never completely fixed but rather fluctuative, transformative and temporary consolidated, can be held and stabilized for sufficiently large time (Bagarello, Haven, Khrennikov, 2017). The possible stable choices (the outputs of stabilization) could be treated within the framework of classical DM, but also quantum DM whose effects are exhibited as “violation of the formula of total probability“ (the classical Bayesian inference scheme is replaced by Quantum Bayesianism). In complex quantum, adaptable dynamic system, probability becomes an abundant oversaturated domain impossible to define in simple terms or content completely and the represented thinking structure (fig.8) is left open to unpredictable DM outputs generated by reconfiguration parameters of the moment-stabilization. Authors of Quantum Probability Theory argue that these kinds of mindsets impact the evolution of mental state which might lead us to the conclusion and the question of a degree in which constructed mental scapes and networks, acting as extended minds (Chalmers and Clark, 1998) could shape the way our biological thinking mechanisms work and evolve.

Quantum coding in, for example, cryptography, produces highly complicated patterns aiming at completely obscuring any logic or pattern recognition. Thus invariance that implies identity of the given system (changing paths of performance by each iteration) becomes extremely provisional, random-like, and arbitrary; system’s performance must not be anticipated.

Emergence property

CAS is emergent, „i.e. it cannot be explained or predicted at the level where the search is carried out“ where it only appears that the state is actually reached (cfr. Heylighen, 1989c) while the process of variation, “blind” but not necessarily random, continues (cfr. Campbell, 1974). In pattern directed

system, theory of the emergence and evolution suggests design of the generic computer support system for solving complex problems and interactions with natural dynamic systems. In both discrete and continuous model, this indicates use of the available (usually incomplete) knowledge, deconstructing and integrating pieces into complexes (CAS), reconfiguring and questioning them with each new input, shaping thereby new temporary consolidated, or transitory knowledge. Departing from the Boolean logic which involves operations in which variables are the truth values true or false usually denoted 1 and 0 (operating further through logical functions of conjunction and, disjunction or, negation not, implication implies, and equivalence), the logical relations of quantum principles operate with all the values inbetween true and false, 0 and 1 – with gradients whose values depend on the temporary, transitory state within the movement, or change they describe. Thus dynamic properties of the elements within the superior condition depicted as (apparently) unregulated scape - a complex system field – would contain multiple choices and valences in constant flux, reconfiguring and restructuring the overall/whole entity (system-object). In architecture, emergent quantum properties opposed to simple systemic decomposability are studied by Resire and Umemoto (2006), Hensel, Menges, and Weinstock (2004, 2010, 2017), all starting with basic propositions from complex system theory and extensive-intensive polarization (Deleuze; De Landa, 2002) applied to spatial structures.

Figure 10: Reiser+Umemoto, Atlas of Novel Tectonics, New York: Princeton University Press, 2006
a. Cartesian Grid and Unstructured Grid, p.26, b. Extensive Difference: Scalar System, Intensive Difference: Gradient Field, p.73
c1. Simple Nested Hierarchy: Whole Reducible to its Parts, Complex Hierarchy: c2 Whole More than the Sum of its Parts, p.51
d1.The Human Scale, p.119, d2 Beyond the Scale of Furniture but Smaller than A House, d3.Larger than a House but Smaller than a Building, p.120; Larger than A building but Smaller than A City, d5.At a Scale of Landscape, d6. the Form Appears Natural Again, p.121

THE ARCHITECTURE OF/AND COMPLEXITY

Usually considered as an inert and static structure with a clear formal (mathematical-physical), programmatic, aesthetic, and social-cultural definition, architecture had to deal with a dynamic condition and an arrangement of complexity or to provide the environment for its transformation and large domain of probable outcomes. As found both in nature and society, when presented as the subject of architectural design and research, various patterns of complex organization are transferred to that level on which it becomes possible to make transpositions and connections between different knowledge systems. Even if speaking of the specific complex phenomena, derived theoretical formulations aimed at defining complexity of the systems without specified content in terms of their relevance to different kinds of complexities observed in social, biological, and physical sciences (Simon, 1962:467). Analogically, abstract explanations and laws of complexities show relevance in architectural research and design - the strategy implies the identification of the ways in which complexities exhibit themselves and perform as found in nature, and the application of this logic to architectural thinking and production – investigation of their meaning, behaviour, and distribution spatially. The most influential and scientifically grounded theories of systems and complexities in architecture thus followed similar movements in all the other disciplines. In 1950s and 1960s, for instance, the global control and research

of the world as a unified system from micro to macro scale, induced significant architectural theories and concepts, such as synergetics, metabolism, structuralism, network society, and different types of interplanetary architectural proposals. More recently, within the second wave of the 20th and 21st century, these evolved in concepts of new structuralism, architecture of constant flux, architecture of the emergence, morphogenetic architecture, etc.

Following Jonas' claims of design as something that "has always possessed the competence to manage complexity" (Jonas, 2007:1) designing complexity through architectural creative projectivity occupies significant position among the various designerly aims. The idea and concepts of architecture or structure in reference to complex systems and generic laws governing their complex dynamic - directing their logic of formation, development, behavior, and appearance – employ universal formulas that reside in the background of complex conditions and processes in a way that can contribute to different spatial problematics, or could be rendered and explained by architectural means as visible forms of their spatial activity. "... A thorough understanding of complex systems requires an understanding of network dynamics as well as network topology and architecture" (Barabasi, 2007). The use of architectural terminology and convergence of architecture and mathematics almost certainly imply possibilities of spatial modelling and analysis of different kinds of complexities using architecture as a research and formalizing device. On the other hand, the existing architectural formations – built spaces (on different scales) – already represent or generate extremely complex effects. They have produced intricacies that require constant reevaluation as many of their consequences develop in an unpredictable way even though a lot of directional elements should maintain emergent dynamics in at least expected domain. Understanding of complex systems and their behavior has always tended towards their control, and here architecture is devised as its means.

Historical representations of complex systems usually attempt to render and map current view of the world and the laws which govern, direct, and control its natural and social relations. These are connected to organizational patterns that order elements and clusters of the system, their operative logic. They are present in sciences, arts, and humanities as their integrative symbolic depiction, but as architecture, they usually use means of geometry and mathematics to translate these codes into a spatial form and distribution.

Figure 11: a. Arbor proportio et proportionalitas, Luca Pacioli, Summa, f. 82r, and Divina proportione : Opera a Tutti Gli ingegni Perspicaci e Curiosi Necessaria. Ove ciascun studioso... (About the Divine Proportions) De Divina Proportione Venice : Paganino Paganini 1509, Part III, Fig.62, Houghton Library, Cambridge MA
 b. Arbor proportio et proportionalitas, by Leonardo da Vinci (adaptation of Pacioli's tree) (da Vinci, Codex Madrid I, f. 78r)
 c. Giambattista Vico Principj di Scienza Nuova [frontispiece 1730 and 1744 editions],
<https://jscholarship.library.jhu.edu/handle/1774.2/33797>
 d. Table of Universal History Eastern Hemisphere 1858,
 e. Shipping routes and Twitter relationships maps, in Bonnett, Alastair. New Views: The World Mapped Like Never Before: 50 maps of our physical, cultural and political world: London: Aurum Press/Quarto Publishing, 2017, p. 162 and p. 154

The term architecture as applied in different sciences, arts and humanities usually has connotations of structure – a distinctive order that articulates and controls properties or a character and behaviour of the subject investigated. It refers to the ruling, generic/"genetic" inner principle and logic of the object-system and the way it holds as a recognizable coherent entity and identity. It is a distinctive "code" that makes a thing precisely the one that it stands for and by which it can be scientifically, artistically, philosophically, or otherwise described in order to bring it closer to human comprehension; It might also exist as something sensible but yet unexplainable in terms of some of our knowledge systems. The knowledge of architecture implies a specific designerly way of knowing (Cross, 1982, 2006) of structure as a guiding rule of its constitution, change and development, numeric or geometric laws

and relations, or its space in terms of formed matter with a distinctive cause, position and function within the world/environment, produced by design.

Formal dynamics: changes in the interactive/responsive surface

Another type of complexity is related to scientific discoveries which allowed many natural phenomena and more complex structures to be mathematically defined, and therefore architecturally applied as numeric and geometric models. Complex patterns from nature, historically frequently used by masterarchitects as mathematical building models (such as the movements and structures of the trees, wind, water, or rain, time cycles inscribed in geological material, etc.) were more methodologically and scientifically explored, becoming thereby more than just an analogy for formal/structural and functional spatial solutions. Complexity theory incorporates dynamics into a structure; therefore architecture of complexity expresses dynamic properties or perform/evolve through time in a specific way, often through interactions formalized in boundary-surface of complex behaviour.

Figure 12 a. b.KalabiYau manifold
 c. Functional SurfaceThe New MathematicsArchitectureJane Burry and Mark Burry, New York: Thames & Hudson, 2010.
 d. Jean Michel Verbeeck, Polygon, <https://www.behance.net/gallery/1014217/Polygon>
 e. Diagram of the physics of liquids. 'Cinématique des fluides.' Archives des sciences physiques et naturelles. 1898.
 f. "Geomtry and Chaos" (Research), Department of Mathematics: Nonlinear and Complex Systems, University of Portsmouth, <http://www.port.ac.uk/departement-of-mathematics/research/nonlinear-and-complex-systems/>

Complex Dynamics and Patterns of Design Thinking/Process

Contemporary architectural representations, interpretations, and constructions include highly intricate assets and creations. Complex imaginative/fictitious systems express high degree of artistic influence, almost reflecting the very creative process, inscribing its traces across the sheets of paper and digital canvases. This complexity includes a lot of subjective features, the authorship, and recognizable personal authority, building this complex identity on the border between the creator/artist-architect, his research questions, and the world of various references (a specific collective and individual memoryscape). In architecture, these are often close to diagrammatic abstractions in visual and thinking representations, which, besides their specific communicative coding, express high aesthetic qualities. These complexities of a design (thinking) process are even more complicated and elusive within the attempt to classify them or establish any kind of pattern-model according to their emergence properties. Their internal logic is hard and complicated to trace, especially when integrating completely undistinguishable, unrecognizable entities (invented or abstracted to the level of unfamiliarity, of almost "alienish" attributes), heading towards innovation. Their intuitive-intellectual balance is always dynamic as in any creative act, but at the end, in all of them, certain sensible regularity or technical and expressive identity, design methodology, or intellectual and artistic paradigm could be distinguished as common issue and key feature for their determination. The key necessary element for definition of this kind of complexity is the author himself and his reflective practice, as well as the outside critical viewpoint which is able to set a comparative relational network between the singular specific case and the current/present, previous/historical, and anticipative markers within the time-scape of human cultural, intellectual, artistic, scientific, technological, and social development. This view may be related to the notion of The Art of System Architecturing coined by Rechtin and Maier.

Considering the sensorial-sensible level, specific visual complexity and aesthetics may be formed as another indicator. Throughout history, artistic practices, or more precisely the practices of visualization, played important role in scientific research and representation. The ability to visualize theoretical models and assumptions and to test them visually supported initial ideas both philosophical and scientific. This field provides enormous source of the ways visual design novelty emerged at the limits of architecture, arts, and sciences.

Figure 13.a. Fig. 2: Adam Bell, *Detailed Evaluation – Britannia Road* detail. An archive, collecting loci, is located within the ward. Drawing of Restored Commonwealth Club, in Bell, Adam. “The Restored Commonwealth Club”, in Allen, Laura and Luke Caspar Pearson (Eds) *Drawing Futures: Speculations in Contemporary Drawing for Art and Architecture* The Bartlett School of Architecture, p.177
 b. Fig. 2: Bryan Cantley, *Native Topography 05/Series 02*. in Cantley, Bryan. “Deviated Futures and Fantastical Histories”, in Allen, Laura and Luke Caspar Pearson (Eds) *Drawing Futures: Speculations in Contemporary Drawing for Art and Architecture* London: The Bartlett School of Architecture, p.185
 c. Bryan Cantley/*Form:uLAF:uBores*, 2012, bottom: *The CAPTCHA of architectural documentation*, in Bryan Cantley. “Two Sides of the Page”. in Spiller, Neil (Ed) *Drawing Architecture* London: John Wiley & Sons, 2013

Architecture as Intensive Science

The logic of dynamic systems is based on nonlinearity, unpredictability, and frequently “discrete knowledge gaps”. The irreducibility of their functioning logic and this kind of non-direct influence including multiple agents and levels of transformation, has challenged many scientific and design research projects. It placed the focus and interest on the idea of control and articulation of something that cannot be numerically (mathematically and physically) defined as completely reliable. The main contribution of our spatial discipline to this topic is made on the borders between formal studies in architecture and mathematics, physics and environmental studies, as well as research in universal principles and logic that underlie investigated phenomena. In literature and design methodologies we can single out numerous publications and approaches dealing with intensities. They are investigated by Reiser and Umemoto (2010), Deleuze (1987), DeLanda (1998, 2000, 2012), Rahm, Oxmans, Lynn, Van Berkel, Novak, Hensel, Menges, Weinstock, and many others. Architecture of variation and intensive gradients marked intellectual movement at the end of 20th century, dealing with intensive complexity and digital fluid dynamics.

“Dynamic laws, expressed in the form of systems of differential or difference equations, have, in a large number of cases, provided the clue for the simple description of the complex” (Simon, 1962:481). The scientific recoding performed by move from extensive toward intensive definitions and a translation of state description into a process description, captures the logic of complex dynamics and adaptability. This kind of analysis includes also different degrees of a system: from locally determining the behaviour of particular characteristics of system’s elements, the interactive profile of element to quality of the system’s operation in general.

On the large scale wide range of areas of astrophysical and geophysical dynamics, from the Earth’s tectonic plates, atmosphere and oceans, planetary atmospheres and planetary interiors, from solar, stellar, and galactic dynamics to astrophysical discs, may influence environmental parameters of architectural and urban intervention and innovation. Our knowledge and understanding of the phenomena of turbulence, waves, instabilities, structures and multiscale dynamics in magnetized

rotating plasma may be the next subject for architectural problematization considering large-scale complexities: perhaps through temporal and spatial scales on which astrophysical phenomena observed by modern instrumentation and monitoring systems, may have impact on built and natural environment.

Figure 14: a. Mandelbrot set
 b, c, d. landforms generated by tectonic activity expressing fractal progressions
 e, f, g. Diagram of the Mandelbrot based Bifurcations, <https://lut.im/hLfHBfb4Qy/OBvHOcs6eVP5RNGc.jpg>
 Diagram of the Mandelbrot based Bifurcations, <https://lut.im/vtGri3gQhd/WGZx3xrlsvxKdlW4.jpg>
 Eisenman Architects, The City of Culture, Galicia, Spain, 2011, cusp catastrophe model as ground-object strategy
 h, i, j. Diagrams of the Mandelbrot based Bifurcations

Diagrammatic Complexity

Artificial systems were constructed in order to explain and deal with the elusive nature of complexity. Diagrammatics, and later diagrammatology, defined the research field which was able to give the appropriate answer to complex reasoning and representation - they have become main devices for modeling complexity. Analysis of existing complicated patterns in nature, society and the whole world as they exist beyond our comprehension and through our creative construction and scientific explanation, is made more elaborate than ever before. Used extensively in history, combinatorics which articulated large number of elements, systematized, and organized data or different scientific systems, found new digital algorithmic interpretation in contemporary mathematics and its various fields of application. Within this category, extensive numeric operations and analyses investigating laws of complex formations are performed. Research area of data-processing is at hand in complex analyses, and diagrams as the most effective instruments of reasoning and representation could be adopted to resolve different complexity issues or variations. Recording or directing logics of distribution, connectivity, and change, diagrammatics approach to initial parameters of architectural ordering of research entity. Whether we speak about datadiagrammatics and their spatial articulation in information figures, or diagrammatical spatial variations and versioning in genesis of architectural form, diagram is elaborated architecturally/structurally as a tool for complex systems application in rendering relational laws of analysed complex situation, or projective creative interpretation of CAS

behaviour, and as a methodological tool for their architectural processing and architectural optimization.

Figure 15 complexity: data and geopolitics
 a. CODE_N, DESIGNED BY CLEMENS WEISSHAAR AND REED KRANZFOR GFT, Hannover, Germany, <http://www.kramweisshaar.com/projects/code-n>
 Retrospective Trending (12.5 terapixel) is a 90 meter-long wall running along the western longitudinal section of the Hall 16. The varicolored scalar field of relation human knowledge, is expressed as a horizontal expansion of 400 frequency timelines from 1800 to 2008, each generated using Google's Ngram tool.
 b. "The World Government" map, is an attempt to understand how world governance behaves, by analyzing its major contributors, from independent states, financial institutions, industrial firms, foundations, schools, universities, NGO's, international organizations, lobbyist groups, religious institutions, and others, in an endless network of influence. Icons represent each of these key players spread throughout the graph, while lines between them represent different types of ties. Bureau d'Etudes, series of mapping projects, aiming at charting and exposing hidden structures of global power and domination

Figure 6. Complexity and Design Strategy
 a. Sharples, Holden, Pasquarelli/Shop (Eds.), *Designing: Evolutionary Technique in Architecture* London: John Wiley & Sons (Academy Press), January 2003,
 b. Graphs of the topology of Usenet, produced Naveen Jamal at Reference.com.
 c. FOA Diagram, Yokohama Port Terminal
 d. Enric Miralles, Eurhythmic Centre, Alicante, Spain, 1993-94, earth movements under entry ramps. The rise and spread of waveforms from A to G and from H to P can be felt through this 'cinematic sectioning'. © Miralles Tagliabue EMBT Studio. in Carpo, *Mathematical Turn in Architecture* (Eds.) London: John Wiley & Sons, 2013, p.94

CONCLUSION: COMPLEXITY BY DESIGN

Design is too complex for complexity science! New tools for design and innovation processes will deal with complexity by designing complexity. These approaches may turn out to be designerly contributions to complexity theory and practice. (Jonas, 2007)

Jonas proposes replacement of modelling by designing (Rittel 1971/1972, Glanville 1982, in Jonas, 2005). Being unable to embed autopoietic properties of natural/social generic and evolutive behaviour patterns by discrete formulas, models are far from the initial state we are trying to explain, holding to their simplified scientific description. Design adds another, creative interpretative level to measuring and scientific profiling of sensible subjects of observation. It includes a large level of creative freedom and constructiveness which might make even bigger moves from the initial condition while only strict scientific models could try to approach the real values of object observed even if slightly differing. If modelling means "designing the problem and the solution simultaneously ..." (Jonas, 2007:6), the explanatory systems will be valid only in constructed or artificial cases produced by created models, or that domain of elusive natural dynamic systems in which the possible error could be neglected as irrelevant. This self-relevance is completely artificial and it seems created merely for its own sake. Design of the solution, on the other hand, without previously defining the problem completely, may anticipate rearrangement of the problem – the problem may comply to the solution; the new

arrangements will be produced through adaptation to replace and abolish previous relations within the complex system dynamics.

Scientific aim was, given the description of some natural phenomena, to find the differential equations for processes that will produce those phenomena. If we have a sufficiently clear description, we can reproduce that object from it (Simon, 1962:480), test the effects and compare the model with the starting complexity phenomena. Thinking and working by design (using creative/designerly methods and techniques), or thinking through design making and engineering with substantial understanding of structural logic, processes and (ir)regularities, can provide valuable insights into complex intricacies, but also produce complexities on its own, moving boundaries of the known and familiar towards imaginative.

Dynagrams: Diagrammatic Modeling of Dynamic Systems Dynamics and Data

Information paradigm by which data represents the key productive asset, taking over most shares in global economy, forms a basis of current flamboyant phase of information revolution. Data is the vital raw material of information economy whose explosive abundance and ubiquity serve as a firm background for the era of data-ism (Brooks in Lohr, 2015). Big-data technology forms one of the most important sources for economy but also philosophy and the way of life. Besides the mechanisms that direct almost every area and activity of contemporary life and the very data-content produced each day, it constitutes new policies and practices that support their maintenance and development, legitimizing this new type/register of digital complexity. And in this case, we do not speak only about the vastness or scale of the virtual data-scape, but intricate relations governing its usability in all the endless dynamics and diagrammatics of functional reactivation of each data-entity. Algorithms of this scape tend to trace and inscribe (temporary consolidate) certain patterns as insights in meaningful assets within the inarticulate information chatter (Speaks, 2000, 2004, 2012) which even if accessible and apparently open, doesn't work until we set the requirement for an organized complexity - a meaningful relational networking including processing, storage, evaluation, memory/consolidation, critical analysis, and economic application.

The last section concludes with a search for an adequate model, design, or descriptive register for construction of interactive environment for complex generative data-system dealing with advanced thinking strategy - its open structure neural network, active interchangeable connectivity pattern and generic relational dynamics. In this way, its design has to advance previous hybrid convergence with quantum logics and dynamics applied to decision-making processes, evolving continuously and updating existing archives by adaptation of their content to novel inferences and networking within the emergent logic of the system's complex field. Theoretical and exemplary research in the field of complex systems, dynamic systemic behaviour, diagrammatics and data-architecture, converging with information and visual sciences, aim at constructing a "living" neural data-scape/field/territory. Working by principles of biological dynamic system, this algorithm should be working as an extended memory and thinking structure (generic mindset) evolving constantly by data-updates, evaluation, and analysis. Based on an interactive design-model, or rather a register of [design] intelligence strategy (Ciric, 2017), a test of this data-field, in a sufficiently open and transformative manner, will capture and visualize real-time variations inscribing them into this designed "consciousness".

Figure 17. design intelligence strategy - neural connectivity in design research, D. Ciric, 2016/17. from research project connected to Doctoral thesis
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